

A Study of Composition of Cobalt Hexammino-Chromithiocyanate—A New Complex Compound

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The conductivity measurement, analysis and IR evidence conclude the composition as $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ —a buff coloured complex compound formed between cobalt hexammino chloride and potassium chromithiocyanate. The measurement of % transmittance with time in mixed solvent of 50% acetone and 50% n-tributyl phosphate shows the decomposition with evolution of NH_3 of the title compound.

In earlier communications¹, the replacement of potassium by different metals and organic bases in potassium chromithiocyanate has been reported. In this paper an attempt has been made to replace potassium by cobalt hexammino ion and to infer the effect on the coordinated groups to both chromium and cobalt metals.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium chromithiocyanate and cobalt hexammino chloride were prepared and standardised by methods adopted by Roesler², Bjerrum³ and Bjerrum and McReynolds⁴. Solutions of different concentrations of potassium chromithiocyanate and cobalt hexammino chloride were prepared fresh each time in conductivity water.

Conductivity measurement.—The conductivity was measured by Philips Model PR 9500 instrument at 20°. Each time 20.0 ml of cobalt hexammino chloride or chromithiocyanate was taken in titrating cell. Direct and indirect titration curves using equimolar solutions (M/50, M/100 & M/500) have been plotted after applying volume correction in Fig. 1. The points of inflection both in case of direct (curves 1, 2 & 3) and reverse (curves 4, 5 & 6) titrations are well pronounced indicating high insolubility of the compound formed in aq. medium.

Composition.—The stoichiometry of the compound formed between cobalt hexammino chloride and chromithiocyanate comes to 1:1. The cobalt hexammino chromithiocyanate was obtained as buff precipitate in above titrations. It was washed with water and dried in air and analysed. [Found: SCN, 60.03; Cr, 8.13; NH_3 , 17.56 and Co, 10.12%. $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires: SCN, 60.12; Cr, 8.09; NH_3 , 17.63 and Co, 10.16%].

Effect of Temperature and Solubility.—The title compound, with practically no change in colour, loses its water when placed in oven at 115°. But at 150° it loses NH_3 and turns blue changing to green on further heating at 180° for 1-2 hrs. The green coloured complex compound again turns to blue when placed in humid ammoniacal

1. Gupta and Anand, *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 599; 1966, **43**, 765.
2. Roesler, *Annalen*, 1867, **141**, 185.
3. Bjerrum, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1921, **118**, 131; 1922, **119**, 51.
4. Bjerrum and Mc Reynolds, *Inorganic Syntheses*, 1946, **2**, 216.

atmosphere. These blue and green coloured complex compounds (study of composition is in progress) partially dissolve in water giving pink colour and light brown precipitate, whereas the same compounds dissolve freely in the mixed solvent of 50% acetone and 50% n-tributyl phosphate.

FIG. 1

The buff coloured cobalt hexammino chromithiocyanate is practically insoluble in water, cold 2N-NaOH, ether, alcohol, acetyl acetate, methyl ethyl ketone, n-tributyl phosphate and n-butyl acetate. But it is partially soluble in acetone and freely soluble in mixed solvents of alcohol-acetone and acetone-n-butyl phosphate.

Absorption and IR spectra.—Absorption of solutions with time of cobalt hexammino chromithiocyanate with and without preheating at 150-60° for 1-2 hrs. has been measured in mixed solvent of 50% acetone and 50% n-tributyl phosphate by H-760 Spekker Absorptiometer in the visible range (Figs. 4 and 3).

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

Absorption spectra of potassium chromithiocyanate, cobalt hexammino chloride and cobalt hexammino chromithiocyanate (curves 1, 2 and 3 respectively in Fig. 2) in KBr phase in the region 700 to 4000 cm⁻¹ were obtained.

DISCUSSION

The stretching frequency of SCN is 2060 cm^{-1} whereas the observed frequency in $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6$ is at about 2170 cm^{-1} . The peak of medium intensity at 1675 cm^{-1} may be due to Cr-S stretching. Hill and Rosenberg⁵ have observed in case of complex cobalt salts bands at approximately 3000 , 1600 , 1350 and 850 cm^{-1} . In spectra of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{Cl}_3$ four bands have been observed at 3250 , 1650 , 1345 and 840 cm^{-1} . Kobayashi and Fujita⁶ attributed a strong band in the neighbourhood of 3000 cm^{-1} to the N-H stretching mode. The formation of the NH_3 -metal bond is associated with a considerable shift of the N-H stretching frequency within the NH_3 . Two fundamentals are expected to appear in the IR for a totally symmetrical octahedral molecule. The bands observed in the neighbourhood of 820 and 1310 cm^{-1} were identified with these fundamentals for the hexammino complexes. In the octahedral $\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6^{3-}$ ion the frequencies are not the same as in $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{3+}$ though both are symmetrical.

In the spectra of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ the characteristic frequencies observed are: 840 (m, symmetric str N-Co-N), 2170 (s, SCN str), 3600 (w, O-H str), 3250 (s, N-H str), 1650 (s, Cr-S str), and a group of four peaks in the range 1340 - 60 cm^{-1} . In case of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{Cl}_3$ only one peak in the range 1340 - 60 cm^{-1} i.e., 1345 cm^{-1} has been observed whereas in the title compound four frequencies, two higher and one lower along with 1345 cm^{-1} have been observed.

In the spectra of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{Cl}_3$ three bands in formation in the region 1340 - 60 cm^{-1} may be noticed which resolved to three peaks along with the band at 1345 cm^{-1} . Since the frequencies of the rocking vibrations of NH_3 are extremely sensitive to the state of the metal-nitrogen bond⁷, the formation of bridging ammino groups may be one of the possibilities as indicating by the appearance in the region of 1340 - 60 cm^{-1} of two high and one low frequency components together with the preservation of frequency at 1345 cm^{-1} —characteristic of the original $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{3+}$ ion; however it requires confirmation.

FIG. 4

In the visible spectra of the solution of cobalt hexammino chromithiocyanate in 50% acetone and 50% n-tributyl phosphate decrease in % transmittance as well as λ_{max} shifting which may be attributed due to decomposition of the compound in solution with time have been observed (Fig. 3). At the start colour of the above solution was observed

5. Hill and Rosenberg, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, **24**, 1219.

6. Kobayashi and Fujita, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1955, **23**, 1354.

7. Evstaf'eva, Baranovskii and Babaeva, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 711.

reddish-brown but within hours light green and after a few days greenish-blue colour was observed. But after heating cobalt hexammino chromithiocyanate at 150° or above greenish-blue colour was observed at the time of dissolution in 50% acetone and 50% n-tributyl phosphate. In this solution decrease in % transmittance but with practically no shifting in λ_{max} with time has been observed particularly in the range 550-600 m μ (Fig. 4). In both cases the final % transmittance is at the same wave length i.e., 600 m μ indicating that in solution of 50% acetone and 50% n-tributyl phosphate cobalt hexammino chromithiocyanate decomposes with slow loss of NH₃.

Sincere thanks of the author are due to Prof. S. M. Mukherji and CDRI, Lucknow for providing facilities and IR respectively.

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Received, April 3, 1967.